

Design and Implementation of an Autonomous Wheelchair with Medical Kit Access Using Raspberry Pi

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Abstract: This paper presents an autonomous wheelchair system designed to enhance the mobility of elderly individuals and people with disabilities through advanced automation and artificial intelligence. Recognizing the importance of independent movement for promoting physical and psychological well-being, this system addresses the challenges faced by those with limited mobility. The wheelchair leverages various sensors to minimize the need for human intervention, thereby fostering autonomy and reducing reliance on caregivers. The system includes an Android interface connected via Bluetooth, allowing for intuitive user interaction and control. Utilizing Raspberry Pi technology, the research aims to create a reliable framework that can adapt to user needs through data processing and analysis. Additionally, the system enables effective communication through head-mounted support, allowing users to record and relay information. Ultimately, this autonomous wheelchair aims to improve mobility and confidence for individuals with disabilities while enhancing their overall independence and quality of life.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Autonomous Wheelchair, Medical Kit, Raspberry Pi.

1 INTRODUCTION

The development of innovative assistive technologies has profoundly transformed healthcare, particularly for individuals with disabilities and the elderly. George Klein's pioneering work on electric wheelchairs during World War II set a precedent for advancements that extend far beyond mobility assistance. Today, the integration of smart technologies into wheelchairs and other mobility devices presents new opportunities to enhance independence and quality of life for users. Research indicates a projected 22% increase in wheelchair users over the next decade, emphasizing the urgent need for high-tech, cost-effective solutions that align with modern technological advancements.

The World Health Organization reports that approximately 285 million people worldwide experience visual impairment, with a significant percentage residing in developing countries. These individuals often face considerable challenges in daily activities, including accessing information and controlling home appliances. To address these issues, a combination of technologies such as Optical Character Recognition (OCR), human assistance, and home automation systems can be employed. A smart home system utilizing the Internet of Things (IoT) can significantly improve the lives of those with disabilities, enabling them to interact with their environment more effectively.

The proposed system in this paper incorporates a central controller that connects home devices to the internet, allowing for voice-activated management through platforms like Google Assistant. This integration enhances user autonomy, enabling individuals to manage their home environments with minimal assistance. Additionally, the development of a smart vehicle designed for the elderly and disabled leverages advanced sensors to facilitate safe, independent travel with minimal human intervention. Furthermore, our healthcare monitoring system utilizes IoT technology to continuously track patient health metrics, such as pulse and temperature. This system employs a medical chamber with automated time management to ensure timely medication delivery, streamlining patient care. Data collected from wearable sensors is uploaded to the cloud, providing healthcare professionals with real-time access to vital patient information, which enhances the quality of care while reducing costs. By fostering seamless communication between medical devices and healthcare providers, this IoT-based system addresses existing gaps in traditional healthcare, enabling proactive monitoring and intervention. The integration of machine-to-machine communication simplifies the complexity of patient data management, allowing for efficient and effective healthcare delivery.

Overall, this multifaceted approach combines mobility, home automation, and healthcare monitoring to create a comprehensive support system for individuals with disabilities and the elderly. By harnessing the power of technology, we can enhance the autonomy and well-being of these individuals, ensuring they lead fulfilling lives with dignity and independence. As this research continues to innovate, the potential for improving the lives of millions becomes increasingly tangible, underscoring the importance of ongoing research and development in this critical field.

2 LITERATURE SURVEY

Research on assistive technologies for wheelchair mobility has made significant strides in recent years. González-Cely et al. [1] explored the use of head movement as a control mechanism for a wheelchair prototype, employing MATLAB and Python simulations to evaluate system response under variable speeds. Building upon the concept of hands-free control, Arshad et al. [2] introduced an electric wheelchair equipped with health monitoring and posture detection capabilities. Their study focused on a portable kit that adapts manual wheelchairs for electric operation, with multimodal control interfaces such as a joystick, voice command, and Android application, enabling personalized support for various disabilities. In contrast, Ma et al. [3] addressed the importance of posture recognition, utilizing a smart cushion with pressure sensors to monitor wheelchair users' positions, thus preventing health issues like pressure ulcers. The study utilized machine learning algorithms to optimize posture detection, achieving a high accuracy rate of 99.47%.

Several studies focused on health monitoring systems to address specific health risks for wheelchair users. Arias et al. [4] proposed a monitoring system to detect vital signs and assess activity levels in real time, which could alert caregivers about the users' physical states. This system proved useful in a two-week trial for monitoring pressure relief and vital signs, showing potential in preventing health risks like heat stroke and inactivity. Fard et al. [5] developed a posture detection system for identifying sitting patterns, aiding in pressure ulcer prevention. Additionally, Liu et al. [6] presented a multi-mode control system that offers manual, voice, and autonomous functionalities, aimed at reducing costs and increasing convenience for various users, including the elderly. These studies demonstrate the importance of adaptable control systems and health monitoring for enhancing the safety and comfort of wheelchair users.

The application of IoT and AI in smart wheelchairs is another significant focus in the literature. Hou et al. [7] designed an IoT-based wheelchair with biophysical sensors to monitor users' vital signs and provide real-time feedback, contributing to elderly healthcare. Further expanding on IoT capabilities, Kumar et al. [8] introduced an autonomous wheelchair model with Raspberry Pi integration for quadriplegic patients, featuring an emergency alert button and RF communication for movement control. Another study by Hou et al. [9] proposed an autonomous wheelchair with AI-based navigation and health data visualization, offering a cloud-based system to analyze users' vital signs and support preventive healthcare. Shamseldin et al. [10] implemented a LIDAR-based autonomous wheelchair with SLAM for navigation, enabling users to set destinations via touchscreen or voice commands. These studies underscore the role of AI and IoT in developing wheelchairs that cater to healthcare needs while promoting independence.

In exploring control mechanisms for autonomous wheelchairs, the integration of alternative navigation and control technologies has been shown to improve accessibility for those with severe physical limitations. Avinaash et al. [11] developed a disaster mitigation robot with LIDAR mapping and AI-enhanced cameras, highlighting the potential for wheelchair applications in dynamic and hazardous environments. Meanwhile, de Jong [12] designed an eye-controlled wheelchair, which addresses the needs of users unable to operate traditional joysticks. The system's usability was confirmed through user tests, though full self-driving capabilities remain an area for further research. Collectively, these studies illustrate a wide range of innovative approaches to wheelchair control and navigation, from eye tracking and head movement to multimodal systems combining IoT, AI, and machine learning for enhanced user support and autonomy.

3 PROPOSED WORK

Hardware architecture refers to the structured arrangement of a system's physical components and their interrelationships. This design model enables hardware engineers to understand how each component integrates into the overall system, facilitating collaboration among various engineering disciplines, such as electrical and mechanical engineering. A well-defined hardware architecture is essential for the successful development and manufacturing of new machines, devices, and components. In this research, the primary hardware component is the Raspberry Pi 3 Model B, which serves as the core of the system. It manages and controls all connected sensors through its software, providing a versatile platform capable of handling multiple operations simultaneously. The Raspberry Pi includes built-in Wi-Fi, allowing for seamless connectivity and enhanced operational efficiency through its kernel services.

Fig. 1 Block Diagram of Autonomous Wheelchair with Medical Kit

The major components connected to the Raspberry Pi in this smart wheelchair system include:

1. **Camera:** Captures visual images, playing a critical role in navigation by helping the wheelchair detect its surroundings and locate the user when needed.
2. **MEMS Sensor:** Monitors the user's health conditions, providing vital data on their physical state.
3. **Solenoid Actuator:** Releases pepper spray in emergency situations, enhancing user safety.
4. **Microphone/Sound Sensor:** Activates the system when the user emits a loud sound, such as a call for help, ensuring prompt responsiveness during emergencies.
5. **Ultrasonic Sensor:** Emits ultrasonic signals to measure distances, helping the wheelchair navigate around obstacles.
6. **DC Motor:** Converts electrical energy into mechanical power, driving the wheelchair's movement.
7. **Vehicle Drivers:** Amplify low signals to high signals necessary for motor operation.
8. **Power Supply Unit (PSU):** A 5V, 1A power supply that converts AC mains into DC power for the internal components.
9. **SD Card:** Functions as a storage device for the operating system and data, providing a compact alternative to traditional hard drives.

To improve system reliability and ease of use, artificial intelligence (AI) can be integrated into the system. AI allows for processing and analysis of the data collected from various sensors, enabling personalized adjustments to the wheelchair's operations. For instance, the system can be trained to recognize specific user commands or environmental conditions, thus streamlining operation for users with disabilities and enhancing overall functionality. By incorporating these elements, the hardware architecture of the autonomous wheelchair offers a comprehensive and efficient system tailored to meet the needs of elderly users and individuals with disabilities. This platform serves as a foundational component for future improvements and expansions, such as advanced AI capabilities and additional safety features.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The autonomous wheelchair system is designed with Raspberry Pi's Raspbian OS, a free, Debian-based operating system optimized for Raspberry Pi hardware. This system offers a versatile platform with over 35,000 pre-installed software packages, making it ideal for developing applications tailored to the Raspberry Pi's capabilities. Initially released in June 2012, Raspbian is continuously updated to improve the performance and stability of its software for Raspberry Pi devices. The integration of multiple sensors and actuators in this wheelchair system is essential for monitoring health metrics, dispensing medication, and providing alerts. Key components and their configurations include:

1. **Infrared (IR) Sensors:**
 - Connected to GPIO pins for user detection and wheelchair operation.
 - First IR sensor: GPIO 16
 - Second IR sensor: GPIO 12 and GPIO 5
2. **Temperature Sensor and Pulse Oximeter:**
 - Both devices are attached to a button for activation and linked to GPIO 0. These sensors are vital for real-time health monitoring.
3. **Buzzer:**
 - Connected to GPIO 13, the buzzer emits alerts for various notifications, including medication reminders.

4. **Camera:**
 - A USB-connected camera captures images for user interaction and health monitoring purposes.
5. **Servo Motors:**
 - Servo motors control the opening and closing of medical chambers, allowing timely dispensing of medication.

The smart wheelchair system offers a range of functionalities aimed at enhancing the user experience and improving health management. These functionalities include:

- **Medication Management:**
 - The Raspberry Pi controller is programmed to trigger the opening of the medical chamber at specified times. This ensures that medication is accessible to the user when needed.
- **Alerts and Notifications:**
 - An auditory alert is generated by the buzzer when it is time for medication intake, helping users maintain their medication schedule.
- **Image Capture and Compliance Monitoring:**
 - While the patient is taking their medication, the system captures an image to document adherence. This image is saved and serves as a record for the caregiver.
- **SMS and Email Notifications:**
 - The IR sensors detect whether the user has taken the medication. Upon detection, the system sends an SMS and an email with the captured image via a Twilio account. Notifications are sent to pre-defined contacts, ensuring caregivers or family members are informed in real-time about the patient's compliance.

Fig. 2 Depicts the autonomous wheelchair with the integrated medical kit. Fig. 3 shows the push button interface with the Raspberry Pi, used for system activation and sensor monitoring. The autonomous wheelchair is designed to assist individuals with mobility impairments, particularly those with limited lower limb control but functional upper limbs. This integration of health monitoring, medication management, and automated alerts significantly improves the user's independence and safety.

Fig. 2 Autonomous Wheelchair with medical kit

Fig. 3 Push button interface with Raspberry-pi

5 CONCLUSIONS

This research demonstrates the successful integration of assistive technology and IoT-enabled healthcare monitoring in an autonomous wheelchair system. The system's capabilities, including real-time health monitoring, medication management, and automated notifications, offer substantial benefits to individuals with limited mobility, particularly those requiring consistent health supervision and medication adherence. By leveraging Raspberry Pi and its compatible sensors, this research establishes a versatile platform for enhancing user independence. The wheelchair's automated medication dispensing, paired with SMS and email notifications, provides a reliable mechanism to ensure that users adhere to their prescribed schedules. This real-time compliance monitoring can significantly reduce the risks associated with missed medication, particularly for elderly or cognitively impaired individuals who may struggle with traditional routines.

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ETHICS STATEMENT

This study did not involve human or animal subjects and, therefore, did not require ethical approval.

STATEMENT OF CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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